

P: ISSN No. 2231-0045
E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438

VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Periodic Research

A Comparative Study of Emotional Intelligence between Male and Female College Students

Paper Id : 20254 Submission Date : 2025-05-10 Acceptance Date : 2025-05-21 Publication Date : 2025-05-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15746085

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/researchtimes.php#8>

Reetu Srivastava

Research Scholar
Psychology
K.S.Saket P.G.College (Dr.
Ram Manohar Lohia
Awadh University)
Ayodhya, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Nidhi Mishra

Assistant Professor
Psychology
K.S. Saket P.G.College
(Dr. Ram Manohar Lohia
Awadh University)
Ayodhya, Uttar Pradesh,
India

Abstract

The present study aims to compare the emotional intelligence of male and female undergraduate college students. For this purpose 'Emotional Intelligence Scale' by Dr. Arun Kumar Singh and Dr. Shruti Narain was administered on 200 male and 200 female students of Lucknow areas. The Mean, Standard Deviation (S.D) and Critical Ratio were calculated of different subareas of emotional intelligence. The results showed that the female college students have significantly better emotional intelligence and understanding motivation than male students. The female students have significantly better emotional intelligence than male college students at 0.01 level.

There is also significant difference of emotional intelligence area as understanding motivation between male and female college students at 0.01 level.

Keywords

Emotional intelligence, cognitive aspect, male and female students.

Introduction

Emotion is a disturbed glandular and muscular activity. It occupies a very important position in a person's life as they motivate many of his endeavour. This is accompanied by physiological and behavioural changes. On the other hand intelligence is the power of perceiving, learning, knowing and understanding.

Emotional intelligence broadens the concept of intelligence beyond the intellectual domain. It includes emotions. Emotional intelligence is a set of skills that sustain accurate appraisal, expression and regulation of emotions.

Emotional intelligence is considered as a key to success present time. Psychologists believe that emotional intelligence is an attribute that help the individual to be more functional to the society. Since emotional intelligence is expected to play a major role in academic success, so it will be desirable to study emotional intelligence among college students.

Intelligence has been defined in many different ways such as in terms of one's capacity for understanding self-awareness, logic, abstract thought, communication, learning, emotional knowledge, memory, planning, creativity and problem solving. It can also be generally described as the ability to perceive or to retain knowledge or information and apply it to itself or other instances of information or knowledge, creating referable understanding models of various size, complexity or density, due to any conscious or sub-conscious imposed will or any instruction to do so. Intelligence is one of the main characteristics that results in individual differences among people.

Although study about intelligence has focussed on its cognitive aspects such as memory, problem solving and thought but now a days, it's non- cognitive aspects such as emotional, social and spiritual ability have been attended by authors. On the other hand, it can be used for predicting individual abilities for success and compatibility in the life.

P: ISSN No. 2231-0045
E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438

VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Periodic Research

Emotional Intelligence (EI) is the ability to monitor a person's own or other people's emotions, to discriminate between different emotions and label them appropriately and to use emotional information to guide thinking and behaviour.

According to Goleman, "Emotional Intelligence is the largest single predictor of success at the workplace."

Components of Emotional Intelligence

1. Self-awareness is the ability to recognize an emotion as it "happens" is the key to your emotional quotient. The major elements of self-awareness are:

*Emotional awareness: It is ability to recognize your own emotions and effects.

*Self –confidence: Sureness about self- worth and capabilities.

2. Self- regulations: it involves

* Self –control: Managing disruptive impulses.

*Trust worthiness: Maintaining the standards of honesty and integrity.

* Conscientiousness: Taking responsibility for own performance.

* Adaptability: Handling change with flexibility.

3. Motivation: Achievement of clear goals and a positive attitude will motivate you.

4. Empathy: It is the ability to recognize how people feel about the importance to success in your life and career.

The more skillful you are at discerning the feelings behind other's signal, the better you can control the signals you send them.

5. Social skills: The development of good interpersonal skill is tantamount to success in your life and career. In today's always connected world, everyone has easy access to technical knowledge.

Emotional intelligence is receiving increasing attention of educators and counsellors for dealing with students who are affected by stresses and challenges of the outside world.

Psychologists and educators are making programmes to improve emotional intelligence of students and these programmes have beneficial effects on their academic achievements. They promote cooperative behaviour and decrease antisocial activities. These programmes are very fruitful in preparing students to face the challenges of life.

Objective of study

To study the significant differences of emotional intelligence between male and female college students.

Review of Literature

Yadav (2011) believed that emotional intelligence is someone's ability to acquire and apply knowledge from his/her emotions and the emotions of others in order to be more successful and lead a more fulfilling life; meanwhile people with a higher emotional intelligence are better performers than those with lower ones.

Rani (2012) found in a study that an individual's emotional intelligence is an indicator of how he or she perceives, understands and regulates emotions, generosity, and sacrifice and so on.

Verma and Dash (2020) studied gender and emotional intelligence of college-going students and found that female students exhibit higher emotional intelligence levels than male students.

P: ISSN No. 2231-0045
E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438

VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Periodic Research

Jonardhanam and Swarnalatha (2021) studied the gender difference in emotional intelligence among male and female students and found significant difference favouring female student.

Pathania and Chopra (2023) also examined the gender difference and found that female students score higher in emotional intelligence components such as empathy and social skills.

Sampling

200 male and 200 female students of Lucknow areas selected through stratified random sampling technique.

Tools Used Emotional Intelligence Scale by Dr.Arun Kumar Singh and Dr. Shruti Narayan

Statistics Used in the Study

Mean, Standard Deviation (S.D) and Critical Ratio of different areas of emotional intelligence.

Result and Discussion

An attempt has been made to study and compare the emotional intelligence of male and female students. For this purpose 'Emotional Intelligence Scale' by Dr. Arun Kumar Singh and Dr. Shruti Narayan was administered on 200 male and 200 female college students. The table exhibited the Mean, Standard Deviation (S.D) and Critical Ratio of different areas of emotional intelligence-

Table showing Mean, S.D and Critical Ratio of emotional intelligence between male and female college students

Different areas of Emotional Intelligence	Gender				Critical Ratio
	Male		Female		
	N=200		N=200		
	Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	
a)Understanding Emotion	2.45	1.03	2.62	0.95	1.70>0.05
b)Understanding Motivation	4.65	1.92	5.65	1.58	5.88<0.01
c)Empathy	6.66	1.66	7.19	1.37	1.04>0.05
d)Handling Relations	6.35	1.81	6.14	1.53	1.23>0.05
Total	20.11	4.06	21.60	3.78	3.82<0.01

Significant Level 0.05 → 1.97

0.01 → 2.59

The table shows that female students have more emotional intelligence (Mean 21.60), while male students have relatively less emotional intelligence (Mean 20.11). The female college students have more understanding emotion (Mean 2.62), more understanding motivation (Mean 5.65), more empathy (Mean 7.19) than male students. The male students have relatively less understanding emotion (2.45), less understanding motivation (Mean 4.65) and less empathy (Mean 6.66) than female students. But the male students have better handling relations (Mean 6.35) than female college (Mean 6.14) students.

To study the significant difference of emotional intelligence between male and female college students, the Critical Ratio was calculated. The Critical Ratio value required to be significant at 0.01 level 2.59 and at 0.05 level 1.97 with degree of freedom 398. It is exhibited in the above table that the obtained value of Critical ratio for emotional intelligence is 3.82, which is significant at 0.01 level. There is significant difference of emotional intelligence between male and female college students at 0.01 level. The female students have significantly better emotional intelligence than male college students at 0.01 level.

There is also significant difference of emotional intelligence area as understanding motivation between male and female college students at 0.01 level. It is shown in table that the obtained value of Critical Ratio for understanding motivation is 5.88, which is significant at 0.01 level. The female college students have significantly better emotional intelligence as understanding motivation than male college students at 0.01 level. But there is no significant difference of emotional intelligence areas as understanding emotion (Critical Ratio 1.53), empathy (Critical Ratio 1.04) and handling relations (Critical Ratio 1.53) between male and female college students at 0.05 level.

The null hypothesis stating that "There is no significant difference of emotional intelligence between male and female students" is rejected. The female college students have significantly better emotional intelligence and understanding motivation than male students at 0.01 level. Although there is no significant difference of emotional intelligence areas as understanding emotion, empathy, and handling relations between male and female college students at 0.05 level.

Conclusion Under the circumstances of the study, it seems that there were significant differences in the emotional intelligence of female and male college students.

Suggestions for the future Study Future studies should take the limitations into account and improve them to get better comparisons. This study will help the students know their emotions as their personality strength. The study would help develop a congenial climate for teaching- learning at the university to develop emotional intelligence of the students.

- References**
1. Antonakis, J. and Ashkanasy, N.M. Dasborough, M. (2009), "Does leadership need emotional intelligence?". *The leadership quarterly* 20(2):247-261.
 2. Hurlock E.B. *Personality Development* (1974).
 3. Baron R.A. *Psychology* 5th edition
 4. John J.B. Morgan and A.R. Gulliland. *The Macmillan company, New York* "An introduction to psychology".
 5. Coleman J.C. *Abnormal Psychology and Modern Life*.
 6. Sandra k. Ciccarelli, J. Noland White, Girishwarb Mishra ISBN 978-93-560-6076-0 'Psychology' 6th edition.
 7. Cabanac Michel (2002) "What is emotion? *Behavioural Processes* 60(2);69-883.
 8. Rani S.S. (2024) *Emotional regulation and gender as key predictors of academic stress among college students. Cogent psychology*, 11(1), 2406640.
 9. Verma P. and Dash P. (2020), *Gender and emotional intelligence of college-going students, International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 8(2).
 10. Janardhanam V. and Swarnalatha T. (2021) *Gender difference in emotional intelligence among male and female students. International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 9(2), 2349-3429.

P: ISSN No. 2231-0045

RNI No. UPBIL/2012/55438

VOL.- XIII , ISSUE- IV May - 2025

E: ISSN No. 2349-9435

Periodic Research

11. *Pathania R. and Chopra G. (2023) Assessment of level of emotional intelligence and gender differences among college students. Himachal Journal of Agricultural Research ,49(1) 45-50.*
12. *<https://www.studocu.com/en-us/document/antioch-university-los-angeles/law-and-science/emotional-intelligence/79840170>*